

A Study on Color-control methods for Work-related space in hospitals

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes color control methods for workspace in hospitals.

For this purpose, it is possible to improve the color environment and establish a guideline for color planning based on objective facts as specific solutions for work-related stress for nurses.

As a first step, this paper focuses on a nurse center where the sharing of medical information takes place. A survey was carried out to check current circumstances of the nurse center, and then a color pallet based on analysis and evaluation of digital pictures is created by using a colorimetric pallet software. Finally, the chromatic pattern that enables to improve the nursing work environment is defined.

This study uses a three steps level examination method, which helps us determine the psychological profile of nursing personnel and how the profile plays an important role in defining possible chromatic patterns that can help reduce the stress present in this working environment. In addition, there are significant advancements in establishing a proper guideline for color planning based on objectives facts.

Keywords: Nurse, Stress, Color Environment

INTRODUCTION

Stress is considered as the plague of our society today. One of the ways to release stress is color therapy and it has extensively been used in hospitals. The role of 'Colors' in hospitals is considered important not only for patient's physical treatments but also for patient's mental care. However, there are many limitations on a potential use of colors. One of the obstacles is due to the lack

of studies that go beyond the analysis of the role of colors in interior design and patients' psychological reactions to it. This makes it harder to develop proper guidelines that can enhance the quality of space and improve both patients' and nursing personnels' daily activities. Hospitals are not only a therapeutic place but also a working place; therefore, their stress levels are highly complexed. According to 'the research of SIGA Diseases of Adults' Center', nurses present the highest levels of stress among all workers in the mentioned center.

Figure1. The Research of SIGA Diseases of Adults' Center about work-related stress in Hospital /2009

Nurses' stress leads to resignation, becoming one of the causes of "Nursing shortage" that the Ministry of Health, Labour and Welfare reported in 2010. Regarding nurses' work-related stress, there are many studies connected to the actual condition of emotional labor, exhaustion and stress factors. However, the solutions for improving the working environment are not yet found. Because of that, this study focuses on the 'interior colors' in nurses' working environment' and 'the role of color in hospitals which are planned to build in near future'. For this purpose, it is possible to establish a guideline for chromatic planning based on

objective facts with specific solutions for nurses' work-related stress.

METHODS USED IN THE STUDY

The ward nurse center in the Kyushu Central Hospital (7ward/330bed) in Fukuoka City is selected for the place to conduct a case study for this three steps investigation. First, we carried out a survey of present working conditions for nurses. Second, we developed a color pallet for the nurse center. Third, we performed an impression evaluation of color simulation based on the color pallet obtained from step two.

Step. 1 Survey	Checking present condition in Nurse center space. Ward Nurse Center in Kyushu Central Hospital(7Ward/330bed)50 Nurses
7.23-8.12.2009	

Step. 2 Color Pallet	Color Pallet of taking pictures in Nurse center space 3th Ward Nurse Center in Kyushu Central Hospital
15:00.8.26.2009	

Step. 3 Impact Evaluation On Color Simulation	Impressing evaluation on color simulation (Munsell Color System) 3th Ward Nurse Center in Kyushu Central Hospital 20 Nurses	
15:00.8.26.2009		
Condition of Simulation		
	Standing	Base element
		Point element
	Sitting	Base element
		Point element
12.4-12.8. 2009		

Figure2. The investigation process in this study

SURVEY OF PRESENT CONDITON IN NURSES' ENVIRONMENT

Based on the results of preliminary interviews, a questionnaire including 13 questions is created. Seven questions are related to day-to-day work of nurses and the remaining questions are regarding color impact (psychological impression) at the nurse center. In total, 50 female nurses who are working at seven locations of the Kyushu Chuo Hospital participated in this questionnaire. They are between 20 and 30 years of age working on their first 4 years of professional activity.

CREATING A COLOR PALLET

According to SUZUKI, "Surrounding visual information will play a major role in maintaining a person's upright posture". In an environment without major changes in the visual information, the visual stimulus is always taken as space location information, and it is used for maintenance of one's posture. The change in such person's position is considered to be strongly connected to the perception of the visual environment. Therefore, at this stage, this study conducted an investigation into how eye level of nurses while working affects on the color environment. The method used for the investigation is as follows. First, a digital picture of nurse center is taken.

Figure3. 360-degree panorama by eye-height when nurse standing and sitting

360-degree panorama

Figure4. Photograph colorimetric pallet software (Color pallet of sitting eye level)

Second, the same image of the picture is created using a colorimetric pallet software from which a color pallet (Munsell color system) is obtained. The 360 degree panoramic images of a nurse both standing and sitting (JIS Standards: Standing eye level at 150 cm and sitting eye level at 120 cm) are taken. The place where we took the images was limited to the 3rd ward nurse center in Kyushu Central Hospital.

nurse center in Kyushu Central Hospital, and the impact evaluation of color simulation covered 20 female nurses belonging to the 3rd ward nurse center. Nurses were asked to choose from 4 possible factors (Value, Activity, Stress, Efficiency) and assign them a degree which resulted in semantic differential method scale(SDMS).

IMPACT EVALUATION ON COLOR SIMULATION

Condition of Color Simulation (Adobe Photoshop CS3.0)			Impact Evaluation	
Standing	Base element	a)Original state	4factor	
		b)Dirt and Poster removal		
Sitting		c)B)with 40% color saturation		
Standing	Point element	Equipment Boxes	Original state	3factor X2values
			Controlled color saturation	
			Controlled hue	
		Uniform	Original state	
			Controlled color saturation	
			Controlled hue	
Sitting	Equipment Shelf	Original state		
		Controlled color saturation		
		Controlled hue		

Figure 5. Condition of simulation and Impact Evaluation

Based on the analysis of the color pallet, a color simulation in order to investigate the impact (impression) of color control was created. The color simulation was limited to the 3rd ward

RESULTS

SURVEY OF CURRENT WORK ENVIRONMENT FOR NURSES

The following three results are obtained on analysis of the questionnaires we collected.

Specific ways to release stress are not given

Figure 6 . Causes of work-related stress

The top answer accounting for 66 % of nurses was that the stress comes from ‘Difficulty of work’. The second answer was ‘Overwork’ followed by such answers as ‘Inefficiency at work’, ‘Opinion a dispute with doctor’ and ‘Lack of communication’.

Some nurses also answered that such stress makes them ‘responsible’, ‘tired’ and ‘nervous’ As for ways to release stress, ‘Chat with co-workers’ was the most common answer followed by the answers such as ‘Put up with stress’ and ‘Cannot relieve stress during work’.

Nurse center is the most restless space in the hospital

Figure 7. The most restless space in the hospital

Figure 8. The most of time attached at white in nurse-center

46% of the nurses answered that the ‘Nurse-center’ is the most restless space in the hospital. The second most common answers were followed by ‘Patients-room’ and ‘Rest-room’. Moreover, the most noticeable color at the nurse center was white and 62% of nurses indicated the white color on the wall. In addition, 63% of them answered that they intend to change the wall color. Consequently, the following four factors are connected in parallel: Noticeable color ≡ White color ≡ Wall ≡ Color.

Nurse center is desired from ‘plain and uncomfortable space’ to ‘warm and comfortable space’

Figure 9. Averaged value difference between present and ideal image at the 3 ward nurse-center

The impact evaluation of three factors including value, activity and stress was conducted to see the present image and the ideal image of the 3rd ward nurse center. The present images of the nurse center included old-fashioned, boring, nothing special, and restless, while ideal images of a nurse center were stylish, lively, friendly, well-lighted, warm and comfortable, and such images are associated with the ‘stress’ factor.

ANLYSIS OF COLOR PALLET

The Base color zone are set according to the color distribution percentage at the 3rd ward nurse center (Photograph: colorimetric pallet software). Based on the results of Survey (Step. one), the wall with Y hue was recognized as white, and it was desired to be changed. We organized equipment such as shelf (hue GY), boxes (hue Y and hue YR) and uniform (hue R) in a focal color outside the range of the base color; however, these colors were seen at other components. In addition, there is a difference in the percentage distribution of the color elements according to eye levels (standing and sitting).

Figure 10. Color pallet of each eye level created based on the images taken at the 3rd ward nurse-center

Analysis of the base element

The result of the impact evaluation based on a color simulation of the predominant base element (wall color) shows a positive image attached to the following simulated conditions (in decreasing order) 'Original state', 'Dirt and Poster removal' and 'Dirt and Poster removal with 40% color saturation'.

The results show similar tendencies for the postures, standing and sitting. Among the four possible factors (Value, Activity, Stress, Efficiency) associated to each simulated state, the stress one presented in the 'Original state' condition, showed the most negative-images, meanwhile the positive-image where attached (in decreasing order) to 'Dirt and Poster removal' and 'Dirt and Poster removal with 40% color saturation'. It is of special attention that through this method was understood that the chromatic variation of the base element (wall color) exert a more predominant influence of the stress factor in conditions that were determined by the standing posture due to its more extended vision range as oppose to the sitting one.

Analysis of the point element

The simulation for the point element was controlled using different values of saturation and hue. Saturation values showed a negative image of the simulation for the other factors different from

'Original state'. In the case of the hue values, it was determined that neighboring colors exert influence depending on the range of the elements.

For instance, the elements of a certain area like 'equipment boxes' give a negative image to hue control. For its part, the inducement of a positive image is possible using certain elements over a wide area such as equipment shelf.

CONCLUSION

The study on color planning in the hospital has been increased since the 1980's and that shows a higher level of considerations for enhancing the patient's comfort. However, there are still concerns remaining in such study that it focuses on patients only and available empirical studies on color planning are insufficient. Against this backdrop, when considering a hospital as 'workspace', the level of a nurse's stress is the highest and there is a growing body of opinion that improvement of working environment for nurses is necessary. Therefore, the color environment in the hospital should be considered as a vital part of the workspace and improved by taking into account psychological conditions of nurses associated with their stress levels. Findings of this study are the following three points.

Factor	Scale value	A)Original state		B) Dirt and poster removal			C) B) with 40% color saturation				
		Standing	Sitting		Average difference with A) (c)	(b)	(c)	(a)	(c)	(b)	(c)
		(a)	(b)	(a)							
Value	Refined (1-2-3-4-5) Vulgar	3.30	3.85	3.40	-0.10	3.50	+0.35	2.80	+0.50	3.55	+0.30
	Modern(1-2-3-4-5) Old fashioned	3.35	3.95	3.35	0.00	3.50	+0.45	2.45	+0.90	3.30	+0.65
Activity	Vibrant (1-2-3-4-5) Dull	3.20	3.30	3.40	-0.20	3.35	+0.05	2.50	+0.70	3.10	+0.20
	Stiff (1-2-3-4-5) Friendly	3.15	3.30	3.25	+0.10	3.25	-0.05	2.90	+0.25	3.20	+0.10
Stress	Anxious (1-2-3-4-5) Relaxed	2.80	2.90	2.90	+0.10	3.10	+0.20	2.85	+0.05	3.10	+0.20
	Cold (1-2-3-4-5) Warm	2.80	3.05	3.05	+0.25	3.15	+0.10	3.50	+0.70	3.37	+0.32
	Relieved (1-2-3-4-5) Stress	3.65	3.85	3.35	+0.30	3.55	+0.30	3.30	+0.35	3.40	+0.45
	Restless (1-2-3-4-5) Pressured	3.75	3.95	3.60	+0.10	3.60	+0.35	3.25	+0.50	3.50	+0.45
	Healthy (1-2-3-4-5) Tired	3.45	4.05	3.45	0.00	3.60	+0.45	2.85	+0.60	3.50	+0.55
	Comfortable (1-2-3-4-5) Uneasy	3.50	3.75	3.35	+0.15	3.30	+0.25	3.15	+0.35	3.30	+0.45
Efficiency	Efficient (1-2-3-4-5) Inefficient	3.50	3.95	3.50	0.00	3.50	+0.45	3.25	+0.25	3.50	+0.45
	Easy (1-2-3-4-5) Hard	3.60	4.10	3.45	+0.15	3.55	+0.55	3.05	+0.55	3.40	+0.70

Figure 11. The average results of the impact evaluation on the base element ('+' is positive-images and '-' is negative-image)

Factor	Scale value	A)Original state		B) 40% color saturation			C) Hue control				
		Standing	Sitting		average difference with A) (c)	(b)	(c)	(a)	(c)	(b)	(c)
		(a)	(b)	(a)							
Value	Refined (1-2-3-4-5) Vulgar	3.25	2.90	3.10	+0.15	3.15	+0.25	2.70	+0.55	2.65	+0.25
	Modern(1-2-3-4-5) Old fashioned	3.20	3.00	3.40	-0.20	3.30	-0.30	2.75	+0.45	2.75	+0.25
Activity	Vibrant (1-2-3-4-5) Dull	3.25	3.00	3.20	+0.05	3.05	-0.05	2.85	+0.40	2.85	+0.15
	Stiff (1-2-3-4-5) Friendly	3.25	3.10	2.85	-0.40	2.65	-0.45	3.30	+0.05	2.90	-0.20
Stress	Cold (1-2-3-4-5) Warm	3.05	3.15	2.60	-0.45	2.90	-0.25	3.30	+0.25	2.95	-0.20
	Restless (1-2-3-4-5) Pressured	2.85	3.05	2.55	-0.30	2.60	-0.45	3.15	+0.30	2.95	-0.10

Figure 12. The average results of the impact evaluation on the point element (Equipment shelf)

It is possible to improve the quality of work environment by changing wall colors at the nurse center.

It is concluded that the properties of color such as saturation, hue and among others that are contained in our 3 steps investigation, are part of the factors that induce a positive perception related to stress levels of nurses at the nurse center. The chromatic pattern in the hospital interior has been changed from white to a low saturated yellow these days because it is effective to reduce nurses' stress due to a negative image of the nurse center. This is best appreciated in the fact that in the new design for the hospital's interior configuration, the designers have taken into account how color excerpt influence over social behavior and have changed the chromatic pattern from white to a low saturated yellow.

In addition, it is considered that a warmer, less stressful environment is created by removing informative printed materials (posters, leaflets, etc.) with the abundant presence of white.

The chromatic configuration varies depending on the eye level of nurses while standing or sitting, and sometimes nurses experience a feeling of oppression.

Analysis of color pallet shows that sitting eye level includes more variety of chromatic configurations such as red and yellow, thereby it is possible to say that the color distribution varies by the eye levels. Furthermore, there is an association between the chromatic configuration at eye level and a feeling of oppression since nurses feel much more oppressed while sitting than standing.

The results of this investigation show that the impact caused by different chromatic configurations is affected depending on the nurses' body posture (standing or sitting) and becomes an important factor that should be taken into account. In addition, we concluded that further investigations necessary in order to obtain more concrete data regarding space circulation, among others.

There is a complex chromatic configuration in the nurse center that interrupts nurses' concentration and efficiency.

Situations at the hospital have been dramatically changed due to digitalization of medical records and nursing cart in recent years, and such changes lead to a change in function of nurse center. Although this case study practiced only at the nurse center of a particular hospital, it was possible to perceive current circumstances of the nurse center where handles both printed materials and electronic data. The study also suggests that the mix of colors in the interior objects (medical devices, computers and etc.) at the nurse center affects nurses' concentration and working efficiency in a negative way. Therefore, it is necessary to sort out more specific color configurations for the nurse center after putting the current circumstances proper perspectives and conducting extensive research on the designs of medical equipment and facility.

Finally, we believe that further investigation using simulated 3D space will significantly expand the range of results obtained with this research (based on 2D simulations), because it will include others factors such as lighting-materials relationship, maximum-minimum space circulation ranges, among others. And it is necessary to carefully take into account the physical properties of the implements used inside the hospitals (furniture, etc.) in order to have an effective correlation between their materials and the chromatic configuration they

posses. In this way, cases such as the negative cold impression caused by metallic implements could be avoided in the future.

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